

Novel explanatory numerical model of a theory to decode water ascent within the xylem passage system

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Abstract

Water ascent is an important issue in the agricultural sciences. Many hypotheses had been developed to explain this matter in a non-living material, namely Xylem. In this paper we had described a model to represent a novel theory of water ascent. The model is simple yet very comprehensive. We had succeeded in producing this model which can be further modified and tuned. More scientific effort is needed to produce a more robust model.

Keywords: water ascent, xylem, agricultural sciences, phloem, pantology

Introduction

Many of theories had been written on the subject of water ascent in the plant. Each theory had weak points. (1) We want to introduce a new theory about this subject. Although this is the raw form of our idea, but we want to make a start point that could be used as prologue to get more scientific effort on this subject. A scientific project will be start in the next period in collaboration with the researchers in the colleges of Agriculture in Iraq to enhance scientific research and apply the latest engineering concept for the sake of humanity.

In order to characterize water ascent in the xylem we should understand these concepts

- Mechanical model of the whole system on the macroscopic scale
- Flow within the channels on the microscopic scale that characterize surge of the fluids
- Backward prevention mechanism. The microscopic structure is acting like tesla valve in aid of interaction of the fluid that had been tuned by the root system with the walls of the passage system

As our model is depending upon the mechanical load of the plant to determine the water ascent, auxetic feature could be one of the unenlightened mechanical features of the xylem passage system to help in providing supplemental mechanism for water raise. We should always assume different models to cover the diversity in the structures of different xylem architecture across the plant kingdom.

Figure 1 complex loads are facing the long plants

The mechanical loads on the tree are extremely complex due to the unique structure of every plant and inherited anisotropy of the trees. (2)

Figure 2 the channels geometry is different across different species

The geometry of the passage system, interconnections between different channels, interaction of the fluid with the channels walls etc. will be peculiar to each plant. The presence of the fluid inside the passage system had tremendous effect on the mechanical properties and is altering the properties of the walls as well as empty tube will behave totally different from that is full. Water is fluid on large scale, but in case of fibrous structure, which is the xylem on the microstructure, the water will behave totally

diffident. The endurance limit of the dry wood is totally differed from that of the living xylem. This is very serious sentence in the context of understanding fatigue properties of the living xylem.

Even when many authors denote the automobility which is partly produced by the physiology or metabolism, these movements should not distract us from the reciprocal effect on of any load whether intrinsic or extrinsic on the movement of the water inside the xylem passage system. (3) The movement will not affect the trunk only, but also to the terminal branches. (4) Ironically, the effect of the gravity had been studies, but the current hypothesizes thesis had been overlooked. (5) This could be a bless to us for being the first authors whom expose this concept to the scientific community for the first time. In order to understand the numerical model of the water ascent, we should a bring these concepts on the table

- The role of root system cells in the modification of fluids that will be ultimately conveyed to and by the xylem. This is a biological aspect
- The architecture of the xylem specialized passage system and correlate it to the both chemistry of the modified fluid and the mechanical properties of the xylem itself. This is a mechanical aspect.

A deeper mechanical aspect that needs deeper investigation is how the currencies of the fluids pass through each part of the passage system individually and at different region of the deformed xylem. We should emphasize upon the mechanism that prevent the back flow of the fluid content inside the xylem passage system. The phloem is the analogue of the epiphysial cartilage in human growth of the bone.

- The total deformation of the passage system is due to the mechanical loads on the planet, namely torsion and bending. These loads are highly complex.

The ever-changing xylem structure will be changed with the advancement of the plant age. Xylem is totally different after decade from that in newly formed at the periphery. This is another a mechanical aspect to be investigated as well as prestrainingng.

To which extent the biology of the phloem affects the mechanical properties of the planet, or even can cause mechanical distortion, should be addressed. This is an additional mechanical aspect.

Explanation of the water fluid transmission within the planet, whether descending or ascending should have both biological aspect and mechanical aspect, and each aspect is acting in collaboration. Theres a delicate balance between both aspects.

We attribute the transport of fluid at early stage of the growth or to the softer part of the plant at its end to the biological capacity of the planet at its end on in the initial growth phases. While the stiffer part or region closer to the root system is closer toward mechanical effect. This is especially sounder after setting and complete a certain period of growth of the planet forming a well-defined trunk. At which level we are shifting from biology to mechanics, this issue should be addressed by the researchers. Regional characterization of the plant needs comprehension of the mechanical and biological aspect. That why we, the biomechanical researchers, are standing to solve such issues. Any load on the plant will be exacerbated at levels closer to the soil. Actually, the plant in its trunk act as Chinese had held fan

Figure 3 this is simple mechanical representation of the plant and closer proximity to the feather structure

All these shapes are close to each other in making the maximum benefit from the effect of the wind and transmit the mechanical load in controlled way to the trunk. The biomechanical concepts are more ubiquitous than we could imagine. The mechanical effect on the root system is accentuated. This is according to the proximity from the trunk. In the current model, we have demonstrated the effect of the mechanical loading on the xylem passage system.

Gradient of stiffness, according to Zainab's law, is not only confined to the animal biology tissue, but also to all other living system. The current model is composed from a simple arrangement with 2 structures. One with modules of elasticity higher than the material of occupying the voids inside of the main model. The voids invested by the main model is a simple model that to present a part of the whole picture. Two types of mechanical model had been tried. Both resulting in extrusion-like movement of the invested material with the lower modules of elasticity.

The chemistry of the ascending fluid in addition to the passage system tightness resulting in an interaction and adsorption of the fluid to the passage channels wall will be enormous. There is certain mechanism that we had attribute the architecture of the xylem passage to stand behind and act as valve mechanism preventing descending of the fluid where it is intended to be raised. Although we had not elucidated this mechanism, but it is highly suggested. We suggest the ascending is to be active, while prevention of the descending is to be passive. At the root system the fluids are actively accumulated, transported to the xylem of the root system and prevented from escape back again to the soil. As we state earlier, at which point this biological pressure will hand over the flag to the mechanical arm is an issue that should be addressed by the researchers. The passage system is not haphazardly arranged, but rather arranged in a fascinating way.

Method

In order to represent our model, we had simplified the xylem structure and passage system. The channels had been represented by long channels which is not related to the actual length of those in a real plant. The septation in the passage system that is perpendicular to the long

axis of the passage system itself had not been represented. The channels radius is uniform and evenly distributed across the model.

Figure 4 the primary sketch that represent the Xylem

Figure 5 the length of the model is 500mm. The channels are continuous and blocked at one end. We suggest a biological mechanism to accomplish such job by blocking the retrograde flow at the root system and permit its flow at the end of the plant

Figure 6 the site of force application is apparent

Figure 7 the bottom of the model is fixed without any permission of the deformation which a theoretical condition

Types of plant tissues

Figure 8 different arrangement of the planet components should be studied well

The relationship of the fluid is tightly control. Rheological properties as well as the descending fluids are tightly controlled. We had studied tow mechanical effects:

- Bending
- Bending associated with torsion

As we have virtual environment and literarily without any limitation, countless assumptions could be made

We suggest the physical model to have stages of region that each region of the trunk will convey the fluids to the next delivering it to the end of the plant. The transition from the xylem to the side branches should be studied and these regions should be characterized well.

Property	Value	Units
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▼ Mechanical properties Elasticity modulus Poisson's ratio Density Ultimate tensile stress Tensile yield stress Compressive yield stress Default failure criterion Thermal expansion coefficient <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▼ Thermal properties Thermal conductivity Specific heat capacity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1.0000000000e+10 3.0000000000e-01 1.2900000000e+03 4.0000000000e+07 3.0000000000e+07 3.0000000000e+07 Not Specified 4.1900000000e-05 2.5000000000e-01 0.0000000000e+00 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> [pa] [dimensionless] [kg/m³] [pa] [pa] [pa] [1/(degree C)] [W/(m*K)] [J/(kg*K)]

Figure 9 the mechanical properties of the very soft material that represent the investing numerical analogue of the xylem

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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▼ Mechanical properties Elasticity modulus Poisson's ratio Density Ultimate tensile stress Tensile yield stress Compressive yield stress Default failure criterion Thermal expansion coefficient <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▼ Thermal properties Thermal conductivity Specific heat capacity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1.0000000000e+06 5.0000000000e-01 1.3400000000e+03 6.0000000000e+07 7.0000000000e+07 9.0000000000e+07 Shear Stress 5.3000000000e-05 4.4000000000e-01 0.0000000000e+00 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> [pa] [dimensionless] [kg/m³] [pa] [pa] [pa] [1/(degree C)] [W/(m*K)] [J/(kg*K)]

Figure 10 the mechanical properties of the very soft material that represent the ascending fluids

Results and discussion

We had depended upon the criteria of displacement to demonstrate the validity of this model.

Figure 11 resultant displacement

Figure 12 enlarged model of bending and torsion

Figure 13 model of only bending

Figure 14 enlarged model of bending

Figure 15 the displacement of the low modulus of elasticity component of the domain. One should also notice that this component here is solid note a fluid

Figure 16 the X field of displacement demonstrate clearly the suggested movement

The figure 9 had clearly show the differences in the displacement at the end of the component with lower modulus of elasticity

Figure 17 the strain representation showing clearly the straining at different region of the inner component with lower modulus of elasticity

Figure 18 minor strain shows clearly the deferential stretching of the inner component

Figure 19 minor strain shows clearly the deferential stretching of the inner component

The deferential compressions stand behind the core of raising

Figure 20 field of the displacement should be always seeked. This is the z displacement field. Z is the equivalent to the long axis of the model

Figure 21 essentially the Von mises stress will be equivocal to other part of the results. This criterion is beneficial in estimation the needed pressure to raise the water and combat the weight of the raised fluids

According to the model in the figure 10 we should emphasize upon the fact that the lower part of the xylem numerical fluid, as well as the fluid which is here represented as solid material with very low modulus of elasticity, is both fixed at the lower end. The real model and backward flow prevention of the fluid is another biomechanical long long long story that should be told.

The current suggested thesis of fluid raising is similar to the that occurring in case of venous drainage from lower limbs in the human being. Many other numerical models iterations had been tried with different results, but represents the same concept, but had not been introduced in this paper. Nevertheless, in the next papers hey well be discussed if Almighty God will.

The non-expansile nature of the passage system that could be deformed with incompressible fluid content that had unique formula prepared by the root system to get special interaction with the walls of the passage system is behind the active mechanical transportation phase of fluid ascent in the xylem, while biological arm had a limited role in delivering, prevention of the retrograde flow at the lower end and receiving at the upper end of the plant. This is the core of the current theory.

Complex mechanical loading will lead different mechanical interaction between the walls of the passage system and the fluid content. We should emphasize upon the fact that these fluids are highly formulated by the root system to be compatible with the specific structure of the xylem passage system walls. Molecular biology should be always correlated with the mechanical profile of the living domains. Unfortunately, our knowledge and understanding in this field specifically still in the infancy stage

Conclusion

We had demonstrated the fluid ascending via a numerical model in dynamic status

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Author profile

Mohammed Zahid Saadoon BDS–FKHCMS (Maxillofacial Surgery). During 2014-2024 he was involved in many researches in biomechanics and biomechatronic. He developed many theories in maxillofacial traumatology, craniofacial growth and dental implantology. He developed a unique dental implant system. He has a special interest in mechanical engineering applications in the medical and dental specialties as well as in forensic medicine. He is now working as maxillofacial surgeon in Ashty teaching hospital, largest secondary referral centers in Soran discrete at Kurdistan region / Iraq.